

M2.2 Appendix 2: E-ARK SIP

E-ARK4ALL
REPORT

Executive Summary

This E-ARK AIP format specification defines the requirements for building Archival Information Packages (AIPs) containing the information to be stored by an archive for the long term. While the AIP format inherits general properties from the “Common Specification for Information Packages” (CSIP), the difference to the Submission Information Package (SIP) and Dissemination Information Package (DIP) is the time dimension: The AIP format defines a generic structure for storing both, a series of information packages, i.e. Submission Information Packages (SIPs), which were transferred at different, subsequent points in time, as well as any changes that needed to be applied for preservation reasons. The AIP format can therefore be seen as a wrapper for information packages which allows recording the provenance of the archival entity concerning changes and sequential submissions (SIPs) over time. Furthermore, an important requirement for creating manageable physical AIP packages is to limit the size of the AIPs. Therefore, the AIP specification defines a practice for splitting very large AIPs into multiple, sub-ordinated parts. Finally, the AIP specification gives a best practice recommendations regarding the physical packaging of AIPs.

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1 Preface

1.1 I. Aim of the specification

This specification is one of several related specifications. The single most important aim of all of these specifications is the provision of a common set of specifications for packaging digital information for archiving purposes. The specifications are based on common, international standards for transmitting, describing and preserving digital data. They have been produced to help data creators, software developers and digital archives to tackle the challenge of short-, medium- and long-term data management and reuse in a sustainable, authentic, cost-efficient, manageable and interoperable way.

The foundation upon which the specifications are built is the Reference model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS) (OAIS Reference model) which has Information Packages as its basis. Familiarity with the core functional entities of OAIS is a prerequisite for understanding the specifications. A visualisation of the current specification network can be seen here:

OAIS Entities

Figure I: Diagram showing E-ARK specification dependency hierarchy.

Specification Aim and Goals

| Common Specification for Information Packages | This document introduces the concept of a Common Specification for Information Packages (CSIP). Its three main purposes are to:

Establish a common understanding of the requirements which need to be met in order to achieve interoperability of Information Packages.

Establish a common base for the development of more specific Information Package definitions and tools within the digital preservation community.

Propose the details of an XML-based implementation of the requirements using, to the largest possible

extent, standards which are widely used in international digital preservation.

Ultimately the goal of the Common Specification is to reach a level of interoperability between all Information Packages so that tools implementing the Common Specification can be adopted by institutions without the need for further modifications or adaptations. || E-ARK SIP | The main aims of this specification are to:

Define a general structure for a Submission Information Package format suitable for a wide variety of archival scenarios, e.g. document and image collections, databases or geographical data.

Enhance interoperability between Producers and Archives.

Recommend best practices regarding metadata, content and structure of Submission Information Packages.

|| E-ARK AIP | The main aims of this specification are to:

Define a generic structure of the AIP format suitable for a wide variety of data types, such as document and image collections, archival records, databases or geographical data.

Recommend a set of metadata related to the structural and the preservation aspects of the AIP as implemented by the reference implementation (eakweb).

Ensure the format is suitable to store large quantities of data.

|| E-ARK DIP | The main aims of this specification are to:

Define a generic structure of the DIP format suitable for a wide variety of archival records, such as document and image collections, databases or geographical data.

Recommend a set of metadata related to the structural and access aspects of the DIP.

|| Content Information Type Specifications | The main aim and goal of a Content Information Type Specification is to:

Define, in technical terms, how data and metadata must be formatted and placed within a CSIP Information Package in order to achieve interoperability in exchanging specific Content Information.

The number of possible Content Information Type Specifications is unlimited. For a list of existing Content Information Type Specifications see, and read more about Content Information Type Specifications in the Common Specification for Information Packages |

1.2 II Organisational support

This specification is maintained by the Digital Information LifeCycle Interoperability Standards Board (DILCIS Board, <http://dilcis.eu/>). The DILCIS Board was created to enhance and maintain the draft specifications developed in the European Archival Records and Knowledge Preservation Project

(E-ARK project, <http://eak-project.com/>) which concluded in January 2017. The Board consists of eight members, but there is no restriction on the number of participants in the work. All Board documents and specifications are stored in GitHub (<https://github.com/DILCISBoard>) while published versions are made available on the Board webpage. Since 2018 the DILCIS Board has been responsible for the core specifications in the Connecting Europe Facility eArchiving Building Block <https://ec.europa.eu/cefdigital/wiki/display/CEFDIGITAL/eArchiving>.

1.3 III Authors

A full list of contributors to this specification, as well as the revision history can be found in Appendix 1.

2 Scope and purpose

To briefly recall the three types of information packages as defined by OAIS (OAIS 2012), there is the Submission Information Package (SIP) which is used to submit digital objects to a repository system; the Archival Information Package (AIP) which allows the transmission of a package to the repository, and its storage over the long-term; and the Dissemination Information Package (DIP) which is used to disseminate digital objects to the requesting user.

In this context, the current document represents the specification of the E-ARK Archival Information Package format (E-ARK AIP, in the following named shortly AIP). It defines the specific requirements for archiving and storing information packages for the long term and focuses on the structural peculiarities and metadata requirements relating to the AIP. Considered in detail, the key objectives of this format are to:

- define a generic structure of the AIP format in a way that it is suitable for a wide variety of data types, such as document and image collections, archival records, databases or geographical data.
- recommend a set of metadata standards related to the structural and the preservation aspects of the AIP.
- ensure the format is suitable to store large quantities of data.
- mitigate the potential preservation risk of repository obsolescence by implementing a repository succession strategy.

3 Relation to other documents

This specification document originates from the document “D4.4 Final version of SIP-AIP conversion component (Part A: AIP specification)” (Faria et al. 2017) created in the E-ARK project (European Archival Records and Knowledge Preservation) which ran from 2014 to 2017 and was funded by the European Commission as part of the Seventh Framework Programme for Research.

The common requirements for all types of E-ARK information packages are defined by the “Common Specification for Information Packages (CSIP) (see Bredenberg et al. 2018)”.

Further documents which are related to the AIP specification in a general sense are listed in the CSIP (section 1.4 “Relation to other documents”).

4 Introduction

The AIP format specification defines a basic structure for storing information packages which are transferred to an archive in form of submission information packages (SIPs). The AIP format provides the means to keep a record of changes that are being applied to an AIP due to metadata edits, digital preservation measures (e.g. migration or adding emulation information), or submission updates.¹

The purpose of defining a standard format for the archival information package is to pave the way for simplified repository migration. Given the increasing amount of digital content archives need to safeguard nowadays, changing the repository solution should be based on a standard exchange format. This is to say that a data repository solution provider does not necessarily have to implement this format as the internal storage format, but it should at least allow exporting AIPs. By this way, the costly procedure of exporting data, producing SIPs, and ingesting them again in the new repository can be simplified. Data repository solution providers know what kind of existing data they can expect if they were chosen to replace an existing repository solution. An E-ARK compliant repository solution should be able to immediately analyse and incorporate existing data in form of AIPs without the need of applying data transformation or having to fulfil varying SIP creation requirements.

Generally, a great variety of repository systems are being developed by different providers, and the way how the AIP is stored depends on specific requirements which have been addressed according to the needs of their respective customers. For this reason, the purpose of this AIP format is not to impose a common storage format that all repository systems need to implement. While it can be used as an archival storage format, it can also be seen as a format that makes system migration easier.

¹A *submission update* is a re-submission of an SIP at a later point in time related to an AIP which contains a previous version of this SIP. Section 5.2.1 explains this concept more in detail.

5 Preliminary definitions and remarks

5.1 Information package (IP)

As already mentioned, the CSIP defines the requirements for concrete package format specifications, such as the SIP, AIP, or DIP. In this sense, an *information package* (IP) is an instance of a format that complies with the CSIP.

5.2 Representations

The concept of “representations” is used according to the definition given in the PREMIS digital preservation metadata standard:

“The set of files, including structural metadata, needed for a complete and reasonable rendition of an Intellectual Entity. For example, a journal article may be complete in one PDF file; this single file constitutes the representation. Another journal article may consist of one SGML file and two image files; these three files constitute the representation. A third article may be represented by one TIFF image for each of 12 pages plus an XML file of structural metadata showing the order of the pages; these 13 files constitute the representation. (PREMIS 2017)”

According to the CSIP, representations are a core concept for all types of IPs. One specific requirement regarding representations in the AIP is that the AIP format must be able, on the one hand, to include representations which are part of the SIP, and, on the other hand, to manage representations which are created during SIP to AIP conversion or as a result of any maintenance operation applying changes to the AIP.

It should also be mentioned that representations can be derived from each other; this is typically the case if digital objects making up a representation are migrated to another format. However, a new representation, in our understanding, does not have to be necessarily the result of a file format migration. It can also consist of a set of instructions included as part of representation metadata explaining how to create an emulation environment in order to render a set of files.

5.3 Logical and physical representation of the AIP

In line with OAIS, we call the logical container of the AIP the complete set of digital objects and metadata representing the conceptual entity as a whole. The conceptual entity must be distinguished from the physical representation of one or possibly more physical containers which represent one conceptual entity.

From the point of view of preserving the integrity of the AIP, the ideal case is that the logical AIP representing the intellectual entity is packaged as one single physical container. This makes recovery easier because the information required to interpret and render the contained representations is bundled together. In reality, however, this is not always possible because the size of the physical container can become very large, and this is the reason for proposing the divided METS structure described more in detail in section 5.1. The divided structure makes it easier to manage representations or representation parts separately.

5.4 Structural division of the AIP

One of the basic requirements formulated by the CSIP is the use of METS as the metadata standard to describe the structure of an IP.

Special attention was given to the fact that it might not be possible to store all representations of an intellectual entity in one physical container, or that even a single representation might have to be divided so that it can be stored on long-term storage media. For this reason, the AIP format describes means to manage representations or representation parts separately.

This structure lays the groundwork for addressing the practical requirement of distributing parts of the intellectual entity over a sequence of physical containers representing a logical AIP. Even though this puts the integrity of the AIP at risk - because in case of disaster recovery the physical container does not represent the complete intellectual entity and dependencies to another (lost) physical container can potentially make it impossible to interpret, understand, or render the content - it is a necessary measure if the amount of data exceeds the capacity limitation of long-term storage media.

5.5 Authenticity of the original submission

The AIP format provides a structure for storing the original submission separately from any data that is created during SIP-to-AIP conversion and during the life-cycle of the AIP. This allows safeguarding the authenticity of the original submission.

However, it is an implementation decision if the original submission is kept “as is” or if the SIP data is adapted during SIP to AIP conversion. In line with OAIS, the content of the original SIP does not have to be identical to the version of the submitted data stored as part of the AIP:

“An OAIS is not always required to retain the information submitted to it in precisely the same format as in the SIP. Indeed, preserving the original information exactly as submitted may not be desirable. (OAIS 2012, 4–52)”

The E-ARK AIP format prescribes a structure by defining a set of requirements and core metadata together with recommendations on how to use the requirements in order to allow changing the AIP while keeping seamless track of the AIP's history.

5.6 Version of an AIP

While the AIP always describes the same unaltered conceptual entity, the way in which this information is represented may change. Therefore the AIP format describes the means to record the provenance from the time of the first submission, and also during the whole life-cycle of the AIP.

For the purpose of the AIP format specification, the *AIP version* concept used is as defined by OAIS:

“AIP Version: An AIP whose Content Information or Preservation Description Information has undergone a Transformation on a source AIP and is a candidate to replace the source AIP. An AIP version is considered to be the result of a Digital Migration. (OAIS 2012, 1–9)”

A new version of an AIP contains one or more new representations which can be either the result of a digital migration or information that enables the creation of an emulation environment to render a representation. The result of this operation is the creation of a new version of the AIP.

The result of a new version of the AIP is stored separately from the submission as explained in detail in section 5.2.2.

Furthermore, the AIP format allows updating the AIP by adding a new version of the submission. This allows supporting the AIP edition which is defined in OAIS as follows:

“AIP Edition: An AIP whose Content Information or Preservation Description Information has been upgraded or improved with the intent not to preserve information, but to increase or improve it. An AIP edition is not considered to be the result of a Migration. (OAIS 2012, 1–9)”

The result of an AIP Edition is stored as part of the submission as explained in detail in section 5.2.1.

5.7 Cardinality of the SIP to AIP transformation

Regarding the transformation of SIPs to AIPs, in the OAIS it is stated that “one or more SIPs are transformed into one or more Archival Information Packages (AIPs) for preservation (OAIS 2012, 2–8)”.

The recommendation in this regard is to guarantee a one-to-one relationship between the logical SIP and the logical AIP whereas the relation of the corresponding physical packages of SIPs and AIPs can be any kind of many-to-many mapping.

6 AIP format specification

The following AIP format specification is defined as a set of requirements² which will be explained with the help of textual descriptions, figures, and concrete examples. It is divided into two parts. On the one hand, there is the structure and metadata specification which defines how the AIP is conceptually organized by means of a folder hierarchy in a file system and a set of metadata standards. And on the other hand, there is the physical container specification which defines the bit-level manifestation of the transferable entity.

6.1 Overview about the CSIP

In the following, we will briefly describe the structure of an IP as defined by the CSIP. Against this background, the AIP format will be introduced as a container format which allows managing the life-cycle of an E-ARK IP that starts with the ingest of an SIP.

As already mentioned in section 4.1, the CSIP relies on the concept of “representations”. Figure 1 gives an example of the structure of an IP with two representations.

²The requirements terminology is based upon RFC2119, “Key words for use in RFCs to indicate requirement levels”, RFC 2119, S. Bradner, March 1997. Available at: <http://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc2119.txt>

Figure 1: Structure of an IP.

Furthermore, Figure 1 shows that metadata can be stored either at the representation level or at the package level. In the CSIP it is explained in more detail where different types of metadata can be stored. In this context, it is sufficient to mention that descriptive, technical, preservation, and rights metadata can relate either to the IP as a whole or to individual representations.

6.1.1 Representations in the AIP

As already mentioned, the structural requirements defined by the CSIP generally apply to the AIP. However, the AIP *representations* folder contains representations which are created as part of the AIP maintenance. If no maintenance operation was performed, this folder is not present. For this reason, the CSIP requirement which prescribes the presence of the *representations* folder is overruled by the following AIP specific requirement.

AIP-REPRESENTATIONS-OPTIONAL: The Archival Information Package (AIP) folder COULD include a folder named representations. This requirement overrules requirement *CSIPSTR9* defined by the CSIP. See also requirement *AIP-REPRESENTATIONS*.

6.1.2 Compound vs. divided package structure

As mentioned, the ability to manage representations or representation parts separately is required because the digital data submissions can become very large. This is not only relevant for storing the AIP, it also concerns the SIP which might need to be divided before the data is submitted to the repository. And regarding the DIP, it requires the capability to reconstruct the DIP from an AIP which is decomposed into multiple parts.

In the following, two approaches for describing the structure of the IP will be described with a focus on requirements of the AIP format: the *compound* structure is represented by one single structural metadata file, and the *divided* structure has one structural metadata file that references those of individual representations. An example will help to describe the two alternatives.

If the *compound* METS structure is used, as shown in Figure 3, a single METS file contains all references to metadata and data files contained in the IP.

Figure 3: One METS file in the root of the package references all metadata and data files

Even though the number suffix of the folders `rep-001` and `rep-002` of the example shown in Figure 3 suggests an order of representations, there are no requirements regarding the naming of folders containing the representations. The order of representations and the relations between them is defined by the structural and preservation metadata. The `representations` folder is mandatory, even for IPs which contain only one representation.

If the *divided* METS structure is used, as shown in Figure 4, then a separate METS file for each representation exists which are referenced by the root METS file. The example shown in Figure 4 has a METS file in the IP's root which points to the METS files `Representations/Rep-001/METS.xml` and `Representations/Rep-002/METS.xml`.

Figure 4: Root METS file references METS files of the different representations

The reason why this alternative was introduced is that it makes it easier to manage representations independently from each other. This can be desired for very large representations, in terms of file size or the amount of files (making the root METS difficult to work with).

As a corollary of this division method we define, on the one hand, a representation-based division as the separation of representations in different folders under the `representations` folder as shown

in the example of Figure 4. And, on the other hand, we define a size-based division as the separation of representation parts. To illustrate this, Figure 5 shows an example where a set of files belongs to the same representation (here named *binary*) and is referenced in two separate physical containers (here named {C1} and {C2} respectively). A key requirement when using size-based division of a representation is that there must not be any overlap in the structure of the representations, and that each sub-folder path must be unique across the containers where the representation parts together constitute a representation entity. Note that for this reason a numerical suffix is added to the representation METS files, to avoid overwriting representation METS files when automatically merging the divided representation back into one single physical representation.

AIP-REP-DIV-NAME: If a representation is divided into parts, the representation component MUST use the same name in the different containers.

AIP-REP-DIV-OVERLAP: If a representation is divided into parts, any overlap MUST be avoided regarding the structure of the representations and each sub-folder path MUST be unique across the containers.

Figure 5: Example of an IP.

For example, let us assume an IP with two representations, each of which consists of a set of three files. In the first representation all data files are in the Open Document Format (ODT) and in the second one - as a derivative of the first representation - all files are in the Portable Document Format (PDF).

6.2 AIP structure

Based on the brief overview about the CSIP given in the previous section, the AIP format specifies a logical structure and guidelines for using METS and PREMIS metadata to create AIPs.

The AIP format offers a structure for storing the complete SIP, and it allows holding data and metadata which are created during SIP to AIP conversion and data that are created during the lifecycle of the AIP.

It is important to note that the AIP format implements the CSIP differently compared to the SIP and the DIP. The SIP and the DIP represent “snapshots in time”, one capturing the state of an information package at submission time (SIP), the other one capturing a specific form of delivery at the point in

time when the information package for access was created (DIP). The AIP, in contrast, allows holding the original submission (snapshot of the IP at submission time), the outcome of preservation actions in the course of the life-cycle separately, and submission updates that occur after the AIP was created.

The main difference is that the AIP is an information package which can contain one or several IPs, namely SIPs. The purpose of this meta-structure is to allow keeping a record of changes to the AIP over time. This requires a specific structure which is not required in the SIP and the DIP. The AIP must therefore not be understood as an extension of the IP (as defined by the CSIP) in the sense that it inherits general properties from the CSIP which are complemented by AIP specific properties. This is the reason why the inherent structure of the AIP is different to the one of the SIP and the DIP.

6.2.1 AIP container for submissions

The AIP format allows storing submissions; having the submission in its original form can help to ensure authenticity of its representations. For this purpose, the AIP format defines a `submission` folder in the root of the AIP which contains the original submission as well as any submission updates added after the AIP was created. The following obligatory requirement applies:

AIP-SUBMISSION-ROOT: The root folder of the AIP package **COULD** contain a `submission` folder which is a container for the original submission and for any updates of SIPs which are submitted after the AIP was created.

If submission updates are enabled for a repository, the submission folder can contain sub-folders with a series of submissions, starting from the original one and followed by the submission updates.

If the submission folder does not contain a METS file, it is assumed that one or several submissions are contained in subfolders.

AIP-SUBMISSION-IP: The `submission` folder **MUST** contain an IP or at least one or several IPs in sub-folders.

AIP-SUBMISSION-IPS: If the `submission` folder contains one or several sub-folders, the sub-folders **MUST** contain IPs.

AIP-SUBMISSIONS-NOMETES: If the `submission` folder contains one or several IPs in sub-folders it **MUST NOT** contain a METS file.

The naming scheme of these sub-folders can be freely defined. However, it should reflect the order of original submission and updates. This means that the folder names should allow alphanumerical ordering, for example, by using zerofill-number suffixes or by deriving the folder name from an ISO 8601 date.

AIP-SUBMISSIONS-ORDER: The sub-folders containing IPs **SHOULD** allow alphanumeric sorting, e.g. by using zero-fill numbers or ISO 8601 date derived strings as part of the folder name.

Examples for submission folder names which allow alphanumerical sorting:

- Zero-fill number suffixes:
 - Submission-00001
 - Submission-00002
 - Submission-00003
- Date/time based strings:
 - 2017-12-25_081012
 - 2017-12-26_083401
 - 2017-12-27_090118
- Date string suffixes:
 - Submission-2017-12-25
 - Submission-2017-12-26
 - Submission-2017-12-27

Figure 6 shows the variant where the `submission` folder contains an IP which represents the original submission. Although this structure does not reflect the version of the submission, the versioning layer can be introduced when the AIP is updated. The IP contained in the submission folder must be moved to a version folder in that case.

Figure 1: Information Package structure

Figure 6: The AIP's "submission" folder containing the IP of the original submission.

Figure 7 shows an example of the alternative structure, where the submission folder contains three sub-folders representing one original submission and two updates which were created over the course of three days.

Figure 7: The AIP containing submissions in subfolders to support submission updates.

For the sake of simplicity, only the first variant, i.e. where the `submission` folder directly contains an IP, is present in the following sections about the AIP structure.

6.2.2 AIP representations

As described in section 5.1 in relation to an IP, one or several representations can be part of an SIP. Additionally, the AIP must be able to include further representations which are either added during SIP to AIP conversion, or through measures which were taken as part of the repository maintenance or for digital preservation purposes.

To illustrate this with the help of an example, Figure 8 shows the structure of an AIP where the original submission consists of two representations which were part of the original submission. The `submission` folder of the AIP contains the original submission “as is”, which means that neither data nor metadata is changed.

Figure 8: AIP representations.

Let us now assume that during SIP to AIP conversion an additional representation is added to the AIP. Figure 9 illustrates an example where an additional `representations` folder exists as a sibling of the `submission` folder which contains a new representation (`rep-001.1`) derived from one of the representations contained in the original submission (`rep-001`).

Figure 9: AIP representations.

This leads to the following requirement regarding representations which are added during SIP to AIP conversion.

AIP-REPRESENTATIONS: If a new representation is added during ingest (SIP to AIP conversion) or created as an AIP preservation measure (AIP to AIP conversion), the root folder of the AIP MUST contain a `representations` folder. For this folder, the same requirements as for the representations of an IP apply.

Note that the three-digit number suffix following the name `rep-` used in the example of Figure 9 indicates the order in time in which the representation of the original submission was created. And the additional number suffix after the dot indicates that the representation is a derivative of the representation identified by the three-digit number before the dot, i.e. `rep-001.1` is the first derivative of representation `rep-001`. This is however for illustration purposes only; the naming of representations does not have to follow such logic.

The AIP is an extension of the IP format; therefore it must follow the basic structure of an IP. Figure 9 shows that the IP components, consisting of METS file, `Metadata` and `representations` folders, are repeated on the AIP level. The extension of the AIP format is basically given by the fact that the AIP is an IP which can contain another IP (here i.e. a SIP) in the `submission` folder.

Note that the `representations` folder in the AIP root folder is optional. It means that this folder must only exist in case representations other than the ones originally submitted are added to the AIP.

The AIP is an IP, therefore the CSIP requirement *CSIPSTR4* applies and the AIP's root MUST contain a METS file that either references all metadata and data files or it references other METS files located in the corresponding representation folders of the AIPs or of the original submission's `representations`.

The METS file which is located in the root folder of the information package is called the *root METS* file.

As a concrete example let us assume a policy stating that PDF documents must generally be converted to PDF/A. Taking the premise formulated in section 4.4 into account that the original submission is not to be changed, the additional representation is added in a *Representation* folder in the root of the AIP as shown in figure 7. Note that this example uses a representation-based division of METS files.

Analogously to Figure 8 there are also two representations in the original submission shown in Figure 10. The first representation (*Rep-001*) consists of a set of files in the Open Document Format (ODT) and the second one (*Rep-002*) is a derivative of the first set of files in the Portable Document Format (PDF). As an example we assume that an institutional policy prescribes that every PDF document must be converted to PDF/A during SIP to AIP conversion. Therefore the second representation (*Rep-002*) was converted to a set of PDF/A files and added to the AIP as an additional representation (*Rep-002.1*).

Figure 10: AIP using representation-based division of METS files.

The two representations of the original submission are located in the *submission/representations* folder of the AIP and the METS file of the submission references the corresponding representation METS files using a relative path to be resolved within the SIP. The root level METS file of the AIP references the METS file of the original submission (*submission/METS.xml*) and the METS file of the new representation (*representations/Rep-002.1/METS.xml*).

6.2.3 Changing the metadata of the original submission

If the originally submitted SIP – as a consequence of an implementation decision – is not supposed to change, then the AIP level metadata folder can contain metadata that relates to representations contained in the original submission. Then, there might be scenarios where the originally submitted metadata needs to be updated.

As an example let us assume that we have to recalculate the checksum during SIP to AIP conversion and that the checksum is recorded as an attribute of the METS file element. As shown in Figure 11, the AIP's *Metadata* folder can – additionally to the existing metadata category folders – contain a *submission* folder with metadata files (here *METS.xml*) that by definition have priority over the ones

contained in the original submission. This means that in case metadata needs to be updated, they must be placed into the root level metadata folder because metadata for the original submission is not allowed to be changed.

Figure 11: METS files in the AIP's `Metadata/submission` folder have priority over the ones contained in the original submission

AIP-MD-PRIORITY: Let `<MDPath>` be a sub-folder-path to a metadata file, then a metadata file under the `AIP/metadata/submission` folder MUST have priority over a metadata file under the `AIP/submission` folder so that `AIP/metadata/submission/<MDPath>` has priority over `AIP/submission/<MDPath>`.

An example is shown in Figure 11 where the METS file in the root of the AIP references an obsolete METS file of the original submission and a current METS file under `metadata/submission`, i.e. the metadata file `AIP/metadata/submission/METS.xml` has priority over the metadata file `AIP/submission/METS.xml`. In this way users have the possibility to consult both the initial metadata and the updated metadata.

6.2.4 Parent-Child relationship

As already pointed out, the divided METS structure was introduced to make the separation of representations or representation parts easier and allow the distribution of these components over a sequence of AIPs.

As shown in Figure 12 The composition of a logical AIP can be expressed by a parent-child relationship between AIPs. It is a bidirectional relationship where each child-AIP bears the information about the parent-AIP to which they belong and, vice versa, the parent-AIP references the child-AIPs.

Figure 12: Parent-child relationship between AIPs

Even though this parent-child relationship could be used to create a hierarchical graph of AIPs, the scope of this specification is limited to a flat list of AIPs which are sub-ordinated to one parent-AIP.

Assuming that a new AIP (e.g. containing an additional representation) needs to be added after parent- and child-AIPs have been stored, the recreation of the whole logical AIP might be inefficient, especially if the AIPs are very large. For this reason, existing child-AIPs remain unchanged in case a new version of the parent-AIP is created. Only the new version of the parent-AIP has references to all child-AIPs as illustrated in Figure 13. As a consequence, in order to find all siblings of a single child-AIP it is necessary to get the latest version of the parent-AIP which implies the risk that the integrity of the logical AIP is in danger if the latest version of the parent-AIP is lost.

Figure 13: New version of a parent-AIP

The result of this process is a sequence of physical containers of child-AIPs plus one additional parent-AIP. The relation of the AIPs is expressed by means of structural metadata in the METS files.

6.3 AIP metadata

The AIP format specifies the use of structural and preservation metadata. Any type of additional metadata, such as descriptive metadata using Dublin Core or EAD³, can be used.

In the following, XML elements are either enclosed between angle brackets (e.g. <fileSpec>) or addressed using XPath syntax (e.g. /mets/metsHdr). In the latter case a leading slash selects a node from the XML document root and the double slash (//) selects nodes in the document from the current node that match the selection, no matter where they are. Also in line with the XPath syntax, element

³Encoded Archival Description, <http://www.loc.gov/ead/>

attributes have a leading '@' character. For example `//mets:file/@USE` denotes the `USE` attribute of a `<file>` element.

6.3.1 Structural metadata

Structural metadata is expressed by means of the METS standard. Some of the high level functions which the standard fulfils in the context of the AIP are the following.

- It provides an overview about the hierarchical structure of the AIP.
- It is an entry point for the AIP, i.e. the first entity to consult to know what an AIP contains and what entities it references.
- It references or embeds any metadata files describing the package as a whole as well as individual content files.
- It contains a complete list of digital objects contained in a package together with basic information to ensure the integrity of the digital objects.
- It establishes links between digital objects and metadata entities (both structural metadata and preservation metadata entities).
- It can hold information about different representations or representation parts belonging to the same intellectual entity.

This section has a focus on METS, therefore, if no namespace prefix is given, the element belongs to the METS default namespace.

METS identifier

Each METS document must be assigned a persistent and (ideally globally) unique identifier. Possible identifier schemes are amongst others: OCLC Purls⁴, CNRI Handles⁵, DOI⁶. Alternatively, it is possible to use a UUID as a locally unique identifier.⁷

Using this identifier, the system must be able to retrieve the corresponding package from the repository.

According to the Common Specification, any ID element must start with a prefix (also, the XML ID datatype does not allow IDs to start with a number, so a prefix solves this issue).

We recommended to use as a prefix an internationally recognized standard identifier for the institution from which the SIP originates. This may lead to problems with smaller institutions, which do not have any such internationally recognized standard identifier. We propose in that case, to start the prefix

⁴<http://purl.org/docs/index.html>

⁵<http://www.handle.net>

⁶<https://www.doi.org>

⁷Universally Unique Identifier according to RFC 4122, <http://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc4122.html>

with the internationally recognized standard identifier of the institution, where the AIP is created, augmented by an identifier for the institution from which the SIP originates.

An alternative to this is to use a UUID:

```
https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc4122
```

The prefix `urn:uuid:` would indicate the identifier type. For example, if the package identifier value is `"123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000"` this would be the value of the METS root element's `OBJID` attribute:

```
/mets/@OBJID="urn:uuid:123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000"
```

The `OBJID` attribute of the root METS is the persistent unique identifier of the AIP.

Digital objects

AIP-DIGITAL-OBJECTS: Any file contained in the AIP is a *digital objects* which MUST be described in a file section (`<fileSec>`) of the METS document.

Listing 2 shows an example of a file section with one file.

```
<fileSec>
  <fileGroup @USE="Common Specification root">
    <file ID="uuid-77146c6c-c8c3-4406-80b5-b3b41901f9d0"
      ADMID="..." MIMETYPE="text/x-sql" SIZE="2862064"
      CHECKSUMTYPE="SHA-256" CHECKSUM="..."
      CREATED="2015-0501T01:00:00+01:00">
      <FLocat LOCTYPE="URL"
        xlink:href="/submission/data/content/file.ext"
        xlink:type="simple"/>
    </file>
  </fileGroup>
</fileSec>
```

Listing 2: Example of a file in the `fileSec` as child of a `fileGroup` element (long attribute values replaced by “...” for readability)

Table 2 lists the attributes of the `<file>` element with an example value. The `/file/FLocat` element provides the link to the actual file.

Attribute	Description	Example Value
file/@ID	<p>Identifier of a file which is part of the AIPFile identifier; must be unique and start with the prefix "ID </p> <p>ID77146c6c-c8c3-4406-80b5-b3b41901f9d0 </p> <p> file/(???) Used to link it to relevant administrative metadata sections that relate to the digital object described.</p> <p>Can be a white space separated list of identifiers. </p> <p>ID4566af74-0f7b-11e5-a6c0-1697f925ec7b
ID4566af74-0f7b-11e5-a6c0-1697f925ec7c </p> <p>file/(???) Hash-sum calculator algorithm SHA-256 file/(???) Hash-sum </p> <p>977fb584d53cd64662dfb br/></p> <p>13dfc58979f51a2703f8621</p> <p> file/(???) Date when the file entry was created . 2014-05-01T01:00:00+01:00 </p> <p>file/(???) Size of the file in bytes. 2498 file/(???) </p> <p>Mime-type application/pdf</p>	

Attribute	Description	Example Value
-----------	-------------	---------------

Table 2: Attributes of the file element

The following rules apply for the URL attribute of the element:

AIP-PATHS-PROTOCOL: The local file paths COULD indicate the protocol part (`file://`), in this case the path must be a valid URI according to RFC3986.⁸

AIP-PATHS-RELATIVE: If the protocol part is omitted, the path MUST be interpreted as a reference relative to the METS document (e.g. `./file.txt` or `file.txt` referring to the file `file.txt` in the current folder).

Additionally, the following requirement applies for compressed files:

AIP-TRANSFORM: If a file is compressed, the `transformFile` element (`//file/transformFile`) SHOULD indicate how the packages have to be processed by means of the attributes 'TRANSFORMTYPE', 'TRANSFORMALGORITHM', and 'TRANSFORMORDER'.

```
<file ...>
  <FLocat xlink:href="../compressed.tar.gz" xlink:type="simple" LOCTYPE="URL"/>
  <transformFile TRANSFORMORDER="1"
    TRANSFORMTYPE="decompression" TRANSFORMALGORITHM="gzip"/>
  <transformFile TRANSFORMORDER="2"
    TRANSFORMTYPE="decompression" TRANSFORMALGORITHM="tar"/>
</file>
```

Listing 3: Compressed file

Referenced Metadata

The use of embedded metadata by using the `<mdWrap>` element is discouraged. Instead, it is recommended to reference metadata by using the `<mdRef>` element.

AIP-METS-MD-REF: External metadata files such as EAD or PREMIS files MUST be referenced by means of the `<mdRef>` element. Its `xlink:href` attribute value must be either a URL relative to the location of the METS root or an absolute URL.

⁸<https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc3986>

Descriptive metadata

The descriptive metadata section (`<dmdSec>`) references descriptive metadata contained in the AIP. Multiple `<dmdSec>` elements are allowed so that descriptive metadata file can be referenced separately within the METS object.

Descriptive metadata is referenced by means of the `<mdRef>` element as part of the descriptive metadata element `<dmdSec>`. Listing 4 shows an example linking to an EAD XML metadata file.

```
<dmdSec ID="uuid-550e8400-e29b-41d4-a716-44665544000a">
  <mdRef LOCTYPE="URL" MDTYPE="EAD" MIMETYPE="text/xml"
    CREATED="2015-04-26T12:00:00+01:00" xlink:type="simple"
    xlink:href="./metadata/EAD.xml"
    CHECKSUMTYPE="SHA-256" CHECKSUM="..." SIZE="2321"/>
</dmdSec>
```

Listing 4: Linking to an EAD XML descriptive metadata file

Administrative Metadata

AIP-METS-MD-AMDSEC: The AIP METS MUST have a single `<amdSec>` element which contains one or several `<digiprovMD>` elements. The `<mdRef>` child of at least one of these elements must be of type PREMIS (`@MDTYPE="PREMIS"`) with the reference to a PREMIS file in the `Metadata` folder of the AIP root.

Listing 5 shows an example with a link to a PREMIS.xml file:

```
<amdSec ID="...">
  <digiprovMD ID="..." @STATUS="CURRENT">
    <mdRef CHECKSUM="..." CHECKSUMTYPE="SHA-256"
      CREATED="..." LOCTYPE="URL" MDTYPE="PREMIS"
      MIMETYPE="text/xml" SIZE="1109"
      xlink:href=" metadata/preservation/premis.xml" xlink:type="
        simple"/>
  </digiprovMD>
</amdSec>
```

Listing 5: Linking to an EAD XML descriptive metadata file

AIP-PREMIS-OBSOLETE: The `@STATUS` attribute value of the `<digiprovMD>` element SHOULD be `SUPERSEDED` if the PREMIS file is obsolete and only included in the AIP to ensure traceability.

AIP-PREMIS-STATUS: The `@STATUS` attribute value of the `<digiprovMD>` element COULD be `CURRENT` to make explicit that the PREMIS file is active.

Structural map

AIP-STRUCTMAP-LABEL: One `<structMap>` with the LABEL attribute value “CSIP structMap” MUST be present in the METS file.

Listing 6 shows a structural map with the LABEL attribute value “Common Specification structural map”.

```
<structMap ID="uuid-f413c073-5b03-4499-830e-8ef724613bef" TYPE="physical"
  LABEL="CSIP structMap">
  <div>
    <div LABEL="submission">
      ...
    </div>
    <div LABEL="representations">
    <div LABEL="representations/rep-001">
      ...
    </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</structMap>
```

Listing 6: Obligatory CSIP structMap

Structural map of a divided METS structure

AIP-DIVIDED-METS: When an AIP uses the divided METS structure, i.e. the different representations have their own METS file, the mandatory `<structMap>` MUST organize those METS files through `<mptr>` and `<fptr>` entries, for each representation. The `<mptr>` node MUST reference the `/<representation>/METS.xml` and point at the corresponding `<file>` entry in the `<fileSec>` using the `<fptr>` element.

```
<structMap ID="uuid-1465D250-0A24-4714-9555-5C1211722FB8" TYPE="PHYSICAL"
  LABEL="CSIP structMap">
  <div ID="uuid-638362BC-65D9-4DA7-9457-5156B3965A18" LABEL="uuid-4422
    c185-5407-4918-83b1-7abfa77de182">
    <div LABEL="representations/images_mig-1">
      <mptr xlink:href="./representations/images_mig-1/METS.xml" xlink:
        title="Mets file describing representation: images_mig-1 of AIP:
          urn:uuid:d7ef386d-275b-4a5d-9abf-48de9c390339." LOCTYPE="URL"
          ID="uuid-c063ebaf-e594-4996-9e2d-37bf91009155"/>
      <fptr FILEID="uuid-fb9c37e7-1c90-4849-a052-1875e67853d5"/>
    </div>
```

```

<div LABEL="representations/docs_mig-1">
  <mptr xlink:href="./representations/docs_mig-1/METS.xml" xlink:
    title="Mets file describing representation: docs_mig-1 of AIP:
    urn:uuid:d7ef386d-275b-4a5d-9abf-48de9c390339." LOCTYPE="URL" ID
    ="uuid-335f9e55-17b2-4cff-b62f-03fd6df4adbff"/>
  <fptr FILEID="uuid-3f2268cd-7da9-4ad8-909b-4f17730dacaf"/>
</div>
</div>
</structMap>

```

Listing 7: Structural map referencing METS files of the different representations

Metadata representation of the AIP structure

Child AIP references parent AIP

The optional reference to a parent AIP is expressed by a structural map with the LABEL attribute value `Parent`. Listing 8 shows an example where a UUID is used as the package identifier and the `xlink:href` attribute has the UUID identifier value of the referenced parent AIP as value. This identifier implicitly references the METS file of the corresponding package. If other locator types, such as URN, URL, PURL, HANDLE, or DOI are used, the `LOCTYPE` attribute can be set correspondingly.

```

<structMap ID="uuid-35CB3341-D731-4AC3-9622-DB8901CD6736" TYPE="PHYSICAL"
  LABEL="parent AIP">
  <div ID="uuid-35CB3341-D731-4AC3-9622-DB8901CD6738" LABEL="AIP parent
    identifier">
    <mptr xlink:href="urn:uuid:3a487ce5-63cf-4000-9522-7288e208e2bc"
      xlink:title="Referencing the parent AIP of this AIP
        (URN:UUID:3218729b-c93c-4daa-ad3c-acb92ab59cee).\"
      LOCTYPE="OTHER" OTHERLOCTYPE="UUID"
      ID="uuid-755d4d5f-5c5d-4751-9652-fcf839c7c6f2"/>
  </div>
</structMap>

```

Listing 8: Using a structMap to reference the parent AIP

Parent AIP references child AIPs

The parent AIP which is referenced by child AIPs must have a structural map listing all child AIPs. Listing 9 shows the structural map of a parent AIP listing four child AIPs.

```
<structMap TYPE="PHYSICAL" LABEL="child AIPs">
  <div LABEL="child AIPs">
    <div LABEL="child AIP">
      <mptr xlink:href="urn:uuid:cea73348-741d-4594-ab8f-0
        b9e652c1099"
        xlink:title="Referencing a child AIP."
        LOCTYPE="OTHER" OTHERLOCTYPE="UUID"
        ID="uuid-d98e416f-55a7-4237-8d45-59c22d221669"/>
    </div>
    <div LABEL="child AIP">
      <mptr xlink:href="urn:uuid:cea73348-741d-4594-ab8f-0
        b9e652c1099"
        xlink:title="Referencing a child AIP."
        LOCTYPE="OTHER" OTHERLOCTYPE="UUID"
        ID="uuid-70f8ec28-23f1-4364-9163-b3e99165b6e6"/>
    </div>
    <div LABEL="child AIP">
      <mptr xlink:href="urn:uuid:3218729b-c93c-4daa-ad3c-
        acb92ab59cee"
        xlink:title="Referencing a child AIP."
        LOCTYPE="OTHER" OTHERLOCTYPE="UUID"
        ID="uuid-77373d7f-e241-481b-bf89-675335beb049"/>
    </div>
    <div LABEL="child AIP">
      <mptr xlink:href="urn:uuid:cea73348-741d-4594-ab8f-0
        b9e652c1099"
        xlink:title="Referencing a child AIP."
        LOCTYPE="OTHER" OTHERLOCTYPE="UUID"
        ID="uuid-3f0cc05c-f27d-499d-a6fd-63bdfed13cb0"/>
    </div>
  </div>
</structMap>
```

Listing 9: Using a structMap to reference the parent AIP

6.3.2 Preservation metadata

As already mentioned, PREMIS (PREMIS 2017) is used to describe technical metadata of digital objects, rights metadata to define the rights status in relation to specific agents or for specific objects, and to record events that are relevant regarding the digital provenance of digital objects.

In the following sections, the PREMIS format and the way that it relates to the METS elements is described in detail. NOTE: in the listings showing PREMIS code parts, the prefix “premis” is omitted (default namespace is the PREMIS namespace⁹) while the “mets” prefix is explicitly added if a relation to the METS file is explained.

Vocabulary

The definition of a vocabulary for PREMIS is an ongoing process, therefore there is no exhaustive list of vocabularies that are to be used exclusively.

The basis of the preservation vocabulary is the preservation schemes provided by the Library of Congress (LoC).¹⁰ Additionally, recent contributions by the PREMIS Implementers Group (which are still “work in progress”) are taken into consideration.¹¹

PREMIS object

The PREMIS object contains technical information about a digital object.

Object identifier

AIP-ID-LOCAL: If an identifier of type `local` is used, this identifier SHOULD be unique in the scope of the PREMIS document.

AIP-ID-OTHER: Other object identifiers of the allowed types COULD be used additionally to the identifier of type `local`.

Listing 10 shows an example of an identifier of type `local`.

```
<objectIdentifier>
  <objectIdentifierType>local</objectIdentifierType>
  <objectIdentifierValue>fileId001</objectIdentifierValue>
</objectIdentifier>
```

Listing 10: Object identifier

Checksums

AIP-PREMIS-CHECKSUMS: Checksums COULD be provided as a descendant of the `objectCharacteristics` element information in form of a SHA-256 hashsum, a fixed size 256-bit value.

⁹Namespace: <http://www.loc.gov/premis/v3>, namespace schema location: <http://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/premis.xsd>

¹⁰<http://id.loc.gov/vocabulary/preservation.html>

¹¹<http://premisimplementers.pbworks.com/w/page/102413902/Preservation%20Events%20Controlled%20Vocabulary>

An example is shown in Listing 11.

```
<fixity>
  <messageDigestAlgorithm>SHA-256</messageDigestAlgorithm>
  <messageDigest>3b1d00f7871d9102001c77f...</messageDigest>
  <messageDigestOriginator>/usr/bin/sha256sum</messageDigestOriginator>
</fixity>
```

Listing 11: Hashsum (value shortened)

File format

AIP-PREMIS-FILE-FORMAT: The format element COULD be provided either using the formatRegistry or the formatDesignation element subelements, or both.

AIP-PREMIS-FILE-FORMAT-PUID: Regarding the formatRegistry, the Persistent Unique Identifier (PUID)¹² based on the PRONOM technical registry¹³ COULD be used.

An example is shown in Listing 12.

```
<format>
  <formatDesignation>
    <formatName>XML</formatName>
    <formatVersion>1.0</formatVersion>
  </formatDesignation>
  <formatRegistry>
    <formatRegistryName>PRONOM</formatRegistryName>
    <formatRegistryKey>fmt/101</formatRegistryKey>
    <formatRegistryRole>specification</formatRegistryRole>
  </formatRegistry>
</format>
```

Listing 12: Optionally, the format version can be provided using the `formatDesignation` element.

Object characterisation

AIP-PREMIS-CHARACTERISATION: The JHOVE¹⁴ technical characterisation result (XML format) COULD be embedded as a descendant of the `objectCharacteristicsExtension` element. An example is shown in Listing 13.

¹²<http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/aboutapps/pronom/puid.htm>

¹³<http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM>

¹⁴<http://sourceforge.net/projects/jhove/>

```
<objectCharacteristicsExtension>
  <jhove>
    ...
  </jhove>
</objectCharacteristicsExtension>
```

Listing 13: JHove digital object characterisation

Original name

AIP-PREMIS-ORIGINAL-NAME: The `originalName` element COULD be used to record the name of an original file.

An example is shown in Listing 14.

```
<originalName>originalfilename.ext</originalName>
```

Listing 14: Original name

Storage

AIP-PREMIS-STORAGE: The storage element COULD hold contain information about the physical location of the digital object.

Ideally this is a resolvable URI, but it can also generally hold information needed to retrieve the digital object from the storage system (e.g. access control or for segmented AIPs).

An example is shown in Listing 15.

```
<storage>
  <contentLocation>
    <contentLocationType>URI</contentLocationType>
    <contentLocationValue>
      /path/to/file.txt
    </contentLocationValue>
  </contentLocation>
  <storageMedium>hard disk HD2253</storageMedium>
</storage>
```

Listing 15: Storage description

Relationship

AIP-PREMIS-RELATIONSHIP: The `relationship` element SHOULD be used to describe relationships of the digital object.

AIP-PREMIS-AIP-INCLUDED: If an AIP is part of another AIP, then the element `relationshipSubType` MUST reference the superordinated AIP.

An example of the latter case is shown in Listing 16.

```
<relationship>
  <relationshipType>structural</relationshipType>
  <relationshipSubType>is included in</relationshipSubType>
  <relatedObjectIdentification>
    <relatedObjectIdentifierType>repository</
relatedObjectIdentifierType>
    <relatedObjectIdentifierValue>
      ID123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000
    </relatedObjectIdentifierValue>
  </relatedObjectIdentification>
</relationship>
```

Listing 16: Relationship

Linking rights statement

AIP-PREMIS-RIGHTS: The `linkingRightsStatementIdentifier` element COULD be used to describe rights statement attached to the object.

For example, only files which have the “discovery right” are being indexed in order to allow these files to be retrievable by the full-text search.

An example of the latter case is shown in Listing 17.

```
<linkingRightsStatementIdentifier>
  <linkingRightsStatementIdentifierType>
    filepath
  </linkingRightsStatementIdentifierType>
  <linkingRightsStatementIdentifierValue>
    metadata/file.xml
  </linkingRightsStatementIdentifierValue>
</linkingRightsStatementIdentifier>
```

Listing 17: Rights statement

PREMIS event

Event identifier

AIP-PREMIS-EVENT-ID: The `eventIdentifier` SHOULD be used to identify events, such as preservation actions, which were applied. An example is shown in Listing 18.

```
<eventIdentifier>
  <eventIdentifierType>local</eventIdentifierType>
  <eventIdentifierValue>PDF to PDF/A</eventIdentifierValue>
</eventIdentifier>
```

Listing 18: Event identifier

Link to agent/object

AIP-PREMIS-EVENT-AGENT: If an event is described, the agent which caused the event (e.g. person, software, hardware, etc.) MUST be related to the event by means of the `linkingAgentIdentifier` element.

In the example shown in listing 20 the SIP to AIP conversion software is linked as agent with identifier value 'Sip2Aip' and the corresponding object is linked by the local UUID value. An example is shown in Listing 20.

```
<linkingAgentIdentifier>
  <linkingAgentIdentifierType>local</linkingAgentIdentifierType>
  <linkingAgentIdentifierValue>
    IngestSoftware
  </linkingAgentIdentifierValue>
</linkingAgentIdentifier>
<linkingObjectIdentifier>
  <linkingObjectIdentifierType>local</linkingObjectIdentifierType>
  <linkingObjectIdentifierValue>
    metadata/file.xml
  </linkingObjectIdentifierValue>
</linkingObjectIdentifier>
```

Listing 20: Link to agent/object

Migration event type

AIP-PREMIS-AGENT: The event by which a resource was created SHOULD to be recorded by means of the `relatedEventIdentification` element.

An example is shown in Listing 21.

```
<event>
  <eventIdentifier>
    <eventIdentifierType>local</eventIdentifierType>
    <eventIdentifierValue>migration-001</eventIdentifierValue>
  </eventIdentifier>
  <eventType>MIGRATION</eventType>
  <eventDateTime>2015-09-01T01:00:00+01:00</eventDateTime>
  <eventOutcomeInformation>
    <eventOutcome>success</eventOutcome>
  </eventOutcomeInformation>
  <linkingAgentIdentifier>
    <linkingAgentIdentifierType>local</linkingAgentIdentifierType>
    <linkingAgentIdentifierValue>
      FileFormatConversion001
    </linkingAgentIdentifierValue>
  </linkingAgentIdentifier>
  <linkingObjectIdentifier>
    <linkingObjectIdentifierType>local</linkingObjectIdentifierType>
    <linkingObjectIdentifierValue>
      metadata/file.xml
    </linkingObjectIdentifierValue>
  </linkingObjectIdentifier>
  <relatedEventIdentification>
    <relatedEventIdentifierType>local</relatedEventIdentifierType>
    <relatedEventIdentifierValue>
      ingest-001
    </relatedEventIdentifierValue>
  </relatedEventIdentification>
</event>
```

Listing 21: Migration event

The event shown in Listing 21 expresses the fact that the object `metadata/file.xml` is the result of the migration event “migration-001” and the event which created the source object is “ingest-001”.

PREMIS agent

AIP-PREMIS-AGENT: Agents which are referenced in events must be described by means of the `agent`

element.

Listing 22 shows a software for indexing named `IndexingSoftware` which supports full text search of the items contained in a package. In this case, the “discovery right” is assigned to this agent.

```
<agent>
  <agentIdentifier>
    <agentIdentifierType>local</agentIdentifierType>
    <agentIdentifierValue>Indexer</agentIdentifierValue>
  </agentIdentifier>
  <agentName>IndexingSoftware</agentName>
  <agentType>Software</agentType>
  <linkingRightsStatementIdentifier>
    <linkingRightsStatementIdentifierType>
      local
    </linkingRightsStatementIdentifierType>
    <linkingRightsStatementIdentifierValue>
      discovery-right-001
    </linkingRightsStatementIdentifierValue>
  </linkingRightsStatementIdentifier>
</agent>
```

Listing 22: Software as an agent

PREMIS rights

AIP-PREMIS-RIGHTS: Rights which are referenced in rights statements MUST be described by means of the `rights` element.

The `rights` element holds information about the rights status of individual digital objects or about agents. An example is shown in Listing 23.

```
<rights>
  <rightsStatement>
    <rightsStatementIdentifier>
      <rightsStatementIdentifierType>
        local
      </rightsStatementIdentifierType>
      <rightsStatementIdentifierValue>
        discovery-right-001
      </rightsStatementIdentifierValue>
    </rightsStatementIdentifier>
    <rightsBasis>Statute</rightsBasis>
    <rightsGranted>
```

```
<act>Discovery</act>
  <restriction></restriction>
</rightsGranted>
</rightsStatement>
</rights>
```

Listing 23: Discovery right statement

6.4 Physical Container Packaging

This part of the AIP format specification gives recommendations regarding the creation of the physical packaging of the logical AIP into either one or multiple transferable and storable entities.

6.4.1 Naming of the packaged entity

According to the requirement defined in section 5.3.1 (“METS identifier”), every AIP bears an identifier which must be recorded in the root METS file of the AIP. By definition, this identifier is the identifier of the AIP itself.

AIP-CONTAINER-ID:: The identifier of the AIP – defined by the attribute **OBJID** of the root METS file’s root element SHOULD be used to derive the beginning part of the file name of the physical storage container.

The file name part which is derived from the AIP’s identifier is called the *AIP file name ID*.

AIP-ID-FILENAME-MAPPING: A specified policy SHOULD be defined which allows deriving a cross-platform, portable file name part from the AIP’s identifier and, vice versa, to infer the identifier from the physical container’s filename.

A first option to implement this requirement would be to limit the characters used in the file name to the “Portable Filename Character Set”¹⁵ which only allows the following character set for saving files:

- Uppercase A to Z
- Lowercase a to z
- Numbers 0 to 9
- Period (.)
- Underscore (_)
- Hyphen (-)

If the identifier of the AIP had characters which do not fall into this character set, then these would need to be mapped into specific ones of the accepted character set.

¹⁵http://pubs.opengroup.org/onlinepubs/9699919799/basedefs/V1_chap03.html#tag_03_282

One proposed way to achieve a bi-directional mapping between identifiers and file names is the pairtree character mapping specification.¹⁶

For example, let us assume the identifier of the AIP was:

```
"urn:uuid:123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000"
```

Then this identifier string would be converted to the folder name because “: -> +” is defined as a single-character to single-character conversion:

```
"urn+uuid+123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000"
```

The packaged entity should also bear this name, e.g. packaged using TAR the name would be:

```
"urn+uuid+123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000.tar"
```

In this example, the AIP’s physical container file name only consists of the AIP file name ID.

AIP-CONTAINER-SUFFIX: Any suffix COULD be added to the physical container file that bears additional information, such as the version, date, sequence number, or the like.

For example, a version number could be added as a suffix to the AIP file name ID as follows:

```
"urn+uuid+123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000_v00001.tar"
```

AIP-CONTAINER-PART: If a physical container contains a part of a superordinate AIP, a suffix COULD be added to the AIP file name ID.

For example, a number for the corresponding part could be added as a suffix to the AIP file name ID as follows:

```
"urn+uuid+123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000_part00001.tar"
```

6.4.2 Packaging

TAR packaging

TAR is an archive file format and also refers to the software `tar` which is a software utility that can be used to bundle up files into one file for being able to transfer archival packages.

AIP-PACKAGE-SINGLEFOLDER: The package content SHOULD be contained in a single folder.

¹⁶<https://tools.ietf.org/html/draft-kunze-pairtree-01> (see section 3: “Identifier string cleaning”)

This means that if a TAR packaged AIP is unpackaged, the content is extracted into a single folder which includes the AIP content.

As an example, let's assume a TAR file with the following name:

"urn+uuid+123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000.tar"

If it is extracted, a folder `urn:uuid:123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000` is created which includes the AIP content, as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: AIP content extracted from a TAR package.

AIP-TARPACKAGE-MANIFEST: In addition to fixity information recorded in the METS file, the AIP COULD include a manifest file (manifest.txt) listing files with MD5 and SHA-256 hashsum.

The manifest file is a text file containing a list of records separated by two line breaks (two carriage return characters (hexadecimal 0D0D) or two times carriage return/line feed (hexadecimal 0D0A0D0A)). A record is a list of named fields, the minimum fields being:

- Name := File path relative to the AIP root
- Size := Size in bytes
- SHA256 := SHA-256 Checksum

- MD5 := MD5 Checksum

An example is shown in Listing 24.

```
Name: METS.xml
Size: 12135
SHA256: d7dec534d2ba5f455391e2ed0cb89db89a2780e0531c83def79b0b0abcb38679
MD5: e94dd23e792bd7e49721a863ad8ed769
Name: metadata/PREMIS.xml
Size: 53719
SHA256: ef01bc59a21f6e99ad3d87b0d25b89d6e8b4915c63dad8791d9490739fe26d4
MD5: 96b85205a9b4b0b5d3c88e2e51b0dc4c
```

Listing 25: Manifest file

AIP-PACKAGE-UNCOMPRESSED: If TAR is used as the packaging format, the content SHOULD be aggregated without compression.

For example, to create a TAR archive without compression for the AIP folder "[urn+uuid+123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000](#)" using the `tar` utility:

```
tar -cf "urn+uuid+123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000.tar" "urn+uuid+123
e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426655440000"
```

BagIt

The BagIt¹⁷ format specifies a set of hierarchical file layout conventions for storage and transfer of arbitrary digital content. It can be used for packaging the AIP.

AIP-PACKAGE-BAGIT: As defined by the BagIt specification, the `bagit.txt` file in the root folder MUST contain the BagIt version and tag file character encoding.

```
BagIt-Version: 0.97
Tag-File-Character-Encoding: UTF-8
```

AIP-PACKAGE-BAGIT-PROFILE: A `bagit-info.txt` MUST be available and valid according to the E-ARK BagIt profile (corresponding to the version of this specification).¹⁸

Example of a `bagit-info` file:

```
BagIt-Profile: https://github.com/DILCISBoard/E-ARK-AIP/blob/{version-tag
}/profiles/bagit/e-ark-bag-profile.json
```

¹⁷<https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc8493>

¹⁸<https://github.com/DILCISBoard/E-ARK-AIP/blob/{version-tag}/profiles/bagit/e-ark-bag-profile.json>

child-AIP file listed in the fetch file SHOULD be listed in every payload manifest.

7 Appendices

7.1 Appendix A - METS referencing representation METS files

```
<fileSec>
  <fileGrp USE="Common Specification root" ID="uuid-0d4f09a8-0734-49fb-9
    bea-dbf6a3f5a444">
    <file MIMETYPE="application/xml" USE="Datafile" CHECKSUMTYPE="SHA-256"
      CREATED="2016-12-14T09:15:24" CHECKSUM="8
        d3f057ac0e45ef173f9ecbfc432b994415c405259aff694632925faf108f541" ID
        ="uuid-3af3e474-991a-4aad-b453-ed3f91d54280" SIZE="2855">
      <FLocat xlink:href="./representations/images_mig-1/METS.xml" xlink:
        type="simple" LOCTYPE="URL"/>
    </file>
    <file MIMETYPE="application/xml" USE="Datafile" CHECKSUMTYPE="SHA-256"
      CREATED="2016-12-14T09:15:24" CHECKSUM="81
        e028df7468ea611b0714148cb607ec74fe1e7914bd762605f38631d21281e9" ID=
        "uuid-e1df6f8b-8cc0-442d-bc45-e61724c63372" SIZE="2873">
      <FLocat xlink:href="./representations/docs_mig-1/METS.xml" xlink:
        type="simple" LOCTYPE="URL"/>
    </file>
  </fileGrp>
</fileSec>
<structMap TYPE="physical" LABEL="CSIP structMap">
  <div LABEL="urn:uuid:7ff70669-73a0-4551-ad5b-12ed9b229e38">
    <div LABEL="submission">
      <!-- removed to improve readability -->
    </div>
    <div LABEL="metadata">
      <!-- removed to improve readability -->
    </div>
    <div LABEL="schemas">
      <!-- removed to improve readability -->
    </div>
    <div LABEL="representations"/>
    <div LABEL="representations/images_mig-1">
      <mptr xlink:href="./representations/images_mig-1/METS.xml" xlink:
        title="Mets file describing representation: images_mig-1 of AIP:
        urn:uuid:7ff70669-73a0-4551-ad5b-12ed9b229e38." LOCTYPE="URL" ID=
```

```

        "uuid-0799bb22-b3b1-4661-b32d-5c2dae0341f9"/>
        <fptr FILEID="uuid-3af3e474-991a-4aad-b453-ed3f91d54280"/>
    </div>
    <div LABEL="representations/docs_mig-1">
        <mptr xlink:href="./representations/docs_mig-1/METS.xml" xlink:title
            ="Mets file describing representation: docs_mig-1 of AIP: urn:
            uuid:7ff70669-73a0-4551-ad5b-12ed9b229e38." LOCTYPE="URL" ID="
            uuid-cc2c70c5-9712-4697-834c-5d5acad47f49"/>
        <fptr FILEID="uuid-e1df6f8b-8cc0-442d-bc45-e61724c63372"/>
    </div>
</div>
</structMap>

```

7.2 Appendix B – METS describing a representation

```

<mets xmlns:ext="ExtensionMETS" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/
XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink" xmlns="
http://www.loc.gov/METS/" PROFILE="http://www.ra.ee/METS/v01/IP.xml"
TYPE="AIP" OBJID="urn:uuid:docs_mig-1" LABEL="METS file describing the
AIP matching the OBJID." xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.loc.gov/METS/
../../schemas/mets_1_11.xsd http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink ../../schemas/
xlink.xsd">
  <metsHdr RECORDSTATUS="NEW" CREATEDATE="2016-12-14T09:15:24">
    <agent TYPE="OTHER" ROLE="CREATOR" OTHERTYPE="SOFTWARE">
      <name>E-ARK earkweb</name>
      <note>VERSION=0.0.1</note>
    </agent>
    <metsDocumentID>METS.xml</metsDocumentID>
  </metsHdr>
  <amdSec ID="uuid-facb861c-5f25-43f7-a1a4-86dfa345a119">
    <digiprovMD ID="uuid-c4113098-6eb5-43f5-9618-6f33ef442400">
      <mdRef MIMETYPE="application/xml" xlink:href="./metadata/
      preservation/premis.xml" LOCTYPE="URL" CREATED="2016-12-14T09
      :15:24" CHECKSUM="
      d9e3bdc2c2e1d1a07cd88585dfddad62cdf40ca060e09456efc68bd2dc88e3a9"
      xlink:type="simple" ID="uuid-2c990270-d140-4d92-8bca-629
      e21926535" MDTYPE="PREMIS" CHECKSUMTYPE="SHA-256"/>
    </digiprovMD>
  </amdSec>
  <fileSec>

```

```
<fileGrp USE="Common Specification representation urn:uuid:docs_mig-1"
ID="uuid-cee0bbc3-ac88-4f21-834e-2c06104141ac">
  <file MIMETYPE="application/pdf" USE="Datafile" CHECKSUMTYPE="SHA
-256" CREATED="2016-12-14T09:15:05" CHECKSUM="
d50fe727b6bed7b04569671a46d4d8a56b93c295afb69703b14c0544286ff86c"
ID="uuid-cf9818bb-567b-44ee-88d8-60a1420feae3" SIZE="2530049">
    <FLocat xlink:href="./data/Suleiman the Magnificent.pdf" xlink:
type="simple" LOCTYPE="URL"/>
  </file>
  <file MIMETYPE="application/pdf" USE="Datafile" CHECKSUMTYPE="SHA
-256" CREATED="2016-12-14T09:15:12" CHECKSUM="3824
fb493235e94bcc3baf33c93a9e4f62d4af387ce055560f01c274ef63da9" ID=
"uuid-3b0e4dcb-727a-44d1-af24-d35676b02bed" SIZE="7603618">
    <FLocat xlink:href="./data/Charlemagne.pdf" xlink:type="simple"
LOCTYPE="URL"/>
  </file>
</fileGrp>
</fileSec>
<structMap TYPE="physical" LABEL="CSIP structMap">
  <div LABEL="docs_mig-1">
    <div LABEL="metadata">
      <fptr FILEID="uuid-2c990270-d140-4d92-8bca-629e21926535"/>
    </div>
    <div LABEL="data">
      <fptr FILEID="uuid-cf9818bb-567b-44ee-88d8-60a1420feae3"/>
      <fptr FILEID="uuid-3b0e4dcb-727a-44d1-af24-d35676b02bed"/>
    </div>
  </div>
</structMap>
<structMap TYPE="logical" LABEL="Simple AIP structuring">
  <div LABEL="Package structure">
    <div LABEL="metadata files">
      <fptr FILEID="uuid-2c990270-d140-4d92-8bca-629e21926535"/>
    </div>
    <div LABEL="schema files"/>
    <div LABEL="content files">
      <fptr FILEID="uuid-cf9818bb-567b-44ee-88d8-60a1420feae3"/>
      <fptr FILEID="uuid-3b0e4dcb-727a-44d1-af24-d35676b02bed"/>
    </div>
  </div>
</structMap>
</mets>
```

7.3 Appendix C - PREMIS.xml describing events on package level

```
<premis xmlns="info:lc/xmlns/premis-v2" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/
XMLSchema-instance" version="2.0" xsi:schemaLocation="info:lc/xmlns/
premis-v2 ../../schemas/premis-v2-2.xsd">
  <object xmlID="uuid-187f239d-c080-4a7f-936d-b35cec4e8ef7" xsi:type="
  representation">
    <objectIdentifier>
      <objectIdentifierType>repository</objectIdentifierType>
      <objectIdentifierValue>urn:uuid:7ff70669-73a0-4551-ad5b-12ed9b229e38
    </objectIdentifierValue>
    </objectIdentifier>
  </object>
  <event>
    <eventIdentifier>
      <eventIdentifierType>local</eventIdentifierType>
      <eventIdentifierValue>IDc5d159d7-2df0-4efe-b07b-559fac4bdc27</
eventIdentifierValue>
    </eventIdentifier>
    <eventType>SIP Delivery Validation</eventType>
    <eventDateTime>2016-12-14T09:14:04</eventDateTime>
    <eventOutcomeInformation>
      <eventOutcome>success</eventOutcome>
    </eventOutcomeInformation>
    <linkingAgentIdentifier>
      <linkingAgentIdentifierType>software</linkingAgentIdentifierType>
      <linkingAgentIdentifierValue>E-ARK Web 0.9.4 (task:
SIPDeliveryValidation)</linkingAgentIdentifierValue>
    </linkingAgentIdentifier>
    <linkingObjectIdentifier>
      <linkingObjectIdentifierType>repository</linkingObjectIdentifierType
>
      <linkingObjectIdentifierValue>urn:uuid:7ff70669-73a0-4551-ad5b-12
ed9b229e38</linkingObjectIdentifierValue>
    </linkingObjectIdentifier>
  </event>
  <agent>
    <agentIdentifier>
      <agentIdentifierType>LOCAL</agentIdentifierType>
      <agentIdentifierValue>E-ARK Web 0.9.4</agentIdentifierValue>
    </agentIdentifier>
    <agentName>E-ARK Web</agentName>
```

```

    <agentType>Software</agentType>
  </agent>
</premis>

```

7.4 Appendix D - PREMIS.xml describing migration events (representation level)

```

<premis xmlns="info:lc/xmlns/premis-v2" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/
XMLSchema-instance" version="2.0" xsi:schemaLocation="info:lc/xmlns/
premis-v2 ../../schemas/premis-v2-2.xsd">
  <object xmlID="uuid-983381f2-edc7-4264-aaf8-10a33dc7a811" xsi:type="
  representation">
    <objectIdentifier>
      <objectIdentifierType>repository</objectIdentifierType>
      <objectIdentifierValue>ID983381f2-edc7-4264-aaf8-10a33dc7a811</
      objectIdentifierValue>
    </objectIdentifier>
  </object>
  <object xmlID="uuid-37b54f97-bef3-4018-abd0-dfd71216fa5f" xsi:type="file
  ">
    <objectIdentifier>
      <objectIdentifierType>filepath</objectIdentifierType>
      <objectIdentifierValue>./data/bluemarble.tiff</objectIdentifierValue
      >
    </objectIdentifier>
    <objectCharacteristics>
      <compositionLevel>0</compositionLevel>
      <fixity>
        <messageDigestAlgorithm>SHA-256</messageDigestAlgorithm>
        <messageDigest>773
        a144dac9ec7844939ce52619b7580d1c7642c7257947d86eaa5f1ffbc7a0</
        messageDigest>
        <messageDigestOriginator>hashlib</messageDigestOriginator>
      </fixity>
      <size>1746308</size>
      <format>
        <formatRegistry>
          <formatRegistryName>PRONOM</formatRegistryName>
          <formatRegistryKey>fmt/353</formatRegistryKey>
          <formatRegistryRole>identification</formatRegistryRole>
        </formatRegistry>
      </format>

```

```
</objectCharacteristics>
<relationship>
  <relationshipType>derivation</relationshipType>
  <relationshipSubType>has source</relationshipSubType>
  <relatedObjectIdentification>
    <relatedObjectIdentifierType>local</relatedObjectIdentifierType>
    <relatedObjectIdentifierValue>../../submission/representations/
images/data/bluemarble.gif</relatedObjectIdentifierValue>
    <relatedObjectSequence>0</relatedObjectSequence>
  </relatedObjectIdentification>
  <relatedEventIdentification>
    <relatedEventIdentifierType>local</relatedEventIdentifierType>
    <relatedEventIdentifierValue>ID27c87d0a-0abd-44e4-bfde-05
fdaa34e620</relatedEventIdentifierValue>
    <relatedEventSequence>1</relatedEventSequence>
  </relatedEventIdentification>
</relationship>
</object>
<event>
  <eventIdentifier>
    <eventIdentifierType>local</eventIdentifierType>
    <eventIdentifierValue>ID27c87d0a-0abd-44e4-bfde-05fdaa34e620</
eventIdentifierValue>
  </eventIdentifier>
  <eventType>migration</eventType>
  <eventDateTime>2016-12-14T09:15:01</eventDateTime>
  <eventOutcomeInformation>
    <eventOutcome>success</eventOutcome>
  </eventOutcomeInformation>
  <linkingAgentIdentifier>
    <linkingAgentIdentifierType>software</linkingAgentIdentifierType>
    <linkingAgentIdentifierValue>Version: ImageMagick 6.7.7-10
2016-06-01 Q16 http://www.imagemagick.orgCopyright: Copyright (C)
1999-2012 ImageMagick Studio LLCFeatures: OpenMP</
linkingAgentIdentifierValue>
  </linkingAgentIdentifier>
  <linkingObjectIdentifier>
    <linkingObjectIdentifierType>local</linkingObjectIdentifierType>
```

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